

Length Biased Two Parameter Suja Distribution with Structural Properties and its Applications

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Abstract

In this present study, we approach a new class of two parameter Suja distribution termed as the length biased two parameter Suja distribution. The proposed new specific distribution derived from the baseline two parameter Suja distribution by employing the length biased technique. Further, the new distribution has been illustrated with comprehensive statistical features like moments, order statistics, Renyi entropy etc. and its parameters are estimated by applying the technique of maximum likelihood estimation. In addition, the predictability and performance of a specific distribution has been evaluated and demonstrated by applying a real lifetime data set to determine its significance.

Keywords: Length biased Distribution, Two parameter Suja distribution, Survival measures, Entropy, Order statistics, Parameter estimation.

1. Introduction

The fundamental significance of weighted distributions has been arisen because of the existence of several experimental problems occur in biased samples by nature in various situations. Infact, it is also observed that the sampling frame for population of various forms is not well defined and therefore recorded observations from these populations are biased and does not follow original distribution unless every observation is given an equal chance of being recorded. The concept of weighted distributions initiated by Fisher (1934) provides an integrative approach to deal with model biased data. The weighted distributions also insists to study how the methods of ascertainment can affect the form of distribution of recorded observations, then subsequently Rao (1965) signifies this idea in an integrated manner while modeling statistical data in which standard distributions were not appropriate to record these observations with equal probability. Weighted distributions have retained a prominent and specified practical importance in probability, statistics and mathematics. Weighted distributions are applied as a tool to introduce some new flexible distributions for modeling real data in different fields. The weighted distribution reduces to the length biased distribution obviously if the weight function considers only the length of the units of interest. Length biased distributions are special case of weighted distributions and hence are widely used in various fields such as survival analysis, reliability studies, biometry, population studies, intermediate events and geological sciences. Sometimes the length biased distributions may occur in several situations because it seems quite impossible to work with truly random sample from population. The concept of length biased distribution was introduced by Cox (1962) and

may arise if there is lack of proper selection among the sample observations. Length biased refers to sample data where the probability of recording an observation depends upon the magnitude of observation and therefore if the observations are selected with probability proportional to their lengths resulting distribution is termed as length biased distribution. The idea of length biased sampling was suggested by Cox (1969) and Zelen (1974) and further the length biased sampling situation depends upon the lack of proper sampling frame.

Many researchers derived and illustrated various important length biased probability distributions along with its applications from various fields. Rashwan (2013) proposed length biased version of generalized gamma distribution. Wani et al. (2022) derived size biased lindley-quasi Xgamma distribution applicable to survival times. Das and Das (2023) presented weighted discretized Frechet-Weibull distribution with application. Al-Kadim and Fadhil (2018) obtained double weighted Lomax distribution. Modi and Gill (2015) developed length biased weighted Maxwell distribution. Al-omari and Alsmairan (2019) studies length biased Suja distribution. Alidamat and Al-omari (2021) derived the length biased two parameter Mirra distribution with engineering data. Mustafa and Khan (2023) developed the length biased extended Rayleigh distribution and its applications. Reyad et al. (2017) obtained the length biased weighted erlang distribution. Ganaie and Rajagopalan (2021) studied the length biased weighted new quasi Lindley distribution with statistical properties and applications. Chaito et al. (2022) described the length biased Gamma-Rayleigh distribution with applications.

The two-parameter Suja distribution is a newly introduced two parametric distribution proposed by Pokalas et al. (2021) obtained from the Lindley and Suja distribution. Its different statistical properties such as survival function, hazard function, mean residual life function, moments, bonferroni and Lorenz curves, entropy measures, stress-strength reliability and stochastic ordering has been discussed. Furthermore, its parameters are estimated through the technique of maximum likelihood estimation.

2. Length Biased Two Parameter Suja (LBTPS) Distribution

The probability density function of two parameter Suja distribution is given by

$$f(x; \theta, \alpha) = \frac{\theta^5}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 24)} (\alpha + x^4) e^{-\theta x}; x > 0, \theta > 0, \alpha > 0 \quad (1)$$

and the cumulative distribution function of two parameter Suja distribution is given by

$$F(x; \theta, \alpha) = 1 - \left(1 + \frac{\theta^4 x^4 + 4\theta^3 x^3 + 12\theta^2 x^2 + 24\theta x}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 24)} \right) e^{-\theta x}; x > 0, \theta > 0, \alpha > 0 \quad (2)$$

Let random variable X represents the non negative condition has probability density function $f(x)$. Consider $w(x)$ be the non-negative weight function, then probability density function of weighted random variable X_w is given by

$$f_w(x) = \frac{w(x)f(x)}{E(w(x))}, \quad x > 0$$

Where $w(x)$ be the non - negative weight function and $E(w(x)) = \int w(x)f(x)dx < \infty$.

Obviously several choices of weight function $w(x)$ gives different weighted distributions. In this paper, we have to obtain the length biased version of two parameter Suja distribution termed as length biased two parameter Suja distribution. Consequently, if weight function $w(x) = x$, the resulted distribution is termed as length biased distribution and its probability density function is given by

$$f_l(x) = \frac{x f(x; \theta, \alpha)}{E(x)} \quad (3)$$

Where $E(x) = \int_0^{\infty} x f(x; \theta, \alpha) dx$

$$E(x) = \frac{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)}{\theta(\alpha\theta^4 + 24)} \quad (4)$$

By applying the equations (1) and (4) in equation (3), we will obtain the probability density function of length biased two parameter Suja distribution as

$$f_l(x) = \frac{x\theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} (\alpha + x^4) e^{-\theta x} \quad (5)$$

and cumulative distribution function of length biased two parameter Suja distribution can be obtained as

$$F_l(x) = \int_0^x f_l(x) dx$$

$$F_l(x) = \int_0^x \frac{x\theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} (\alpha + x^4) e^{-\theta x} dx$$

$$F_l(x) = \frac{1}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} \int_0^x x\theta^6 (\alpha + x^4) e^{-\theta x} dx$$

$$F_l(x) = \frac{1}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} \left(\alpha\theta^6 \int_0^x x e^{-\theta x} dx + \theta^6 \int_0^x x^5 e^{-\theta x} dx \right) \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Put } \theta x = t \Rightarrow \theta dx = dt \Rightarrow dx = \frac{dt}{\theta}, \text{ Also } x = \frac{t}{\theta}$$

As $x \rightarrow x, t \rightarrow \theta x$ and as $x \rightarrow 0, t \rightarrow 0$

After the simplification of equation (6), we will obtain the cumulative distribution function of length biased two parameter Suja distribution as

$$F_l(x) = \frac{1}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} (\alpha\theta^4 \gamma(2, \theta x) + \gamma(6, \theta x)) \tag{7}$$

Fig.1:Pdf plot of Length Biased Two Parameter Suja Distribution

Fig.2:Cdf plot of Length Biased Two Parameter Suja Distribution

3. Survival Analysis

In this section, we will have described the survival function, hazard rate function, reverse hazard rate function and Mills ratio of length biased two parameter Suja distribution.

a. Survival function

The survival or reliability function of length biased two parameter Suja distribution is given by

$$S(x) = 1 - F_l(x)$$

$$S(x) = 1 - \frac{1}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} (\alpha\theta^4 \gamma(2, \theta x) + \gamma(6, \theta x))$$

b. Hazard function

The hazard function is also known as hazard rate or force of mortality and is given by

$$h(x) = \frac{f_l(x)}{1 - F_l(x)}$$

$$h(x) = \frac{x\theta^6(\alpha + x^4)e^{-\theta x}}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120) - (\alpha\theta^4 \gamma(2, \theta x) + \gamma(6, \theta x))}$$

c. Reverse hazard function

The reverse hazard rate function is given by

$$h_r(x) = \frac{f_l(x)}{F_l(x)}$$

$$h_r(x) = \frac{x\theta^6(\alpha + x^4)e^{-\theta x}}{(\alpha\theta^4\gamma(2, \theta x) + \gamma(6, \theta x))}$$

d. Mills Ratio

$$M.R = \frac{1}{h_r(x)} = \frac{(\alpha\theta^4\gamma(2, \theta x) + \gamma(6, \theta x))}{x\theta^6(\alpha + x^4)e^{-\theta x}}$$

Fig.3:Survival plot of Length Biased Two Parameter Suja Distribution

Fig.4:Hazard Plot of Length Biased Two Parameter Suja Distribution

4. Order Statistics

Order statistics is a fundamental concept and it deals with the domain of various statistical sciences. Suppose $X_{(1)}, X_{(2)}, \dots, X_{(n)}$ be the order statistics of a random sample X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n from a continuous distribution with probability density function $f_x(x)$ and cumulative distribution function $F_X(x)$, then the probability density function of r^{th} order statistics $X_{(r)}$ is given by

$$f_{x(r)}(x) = \frac{n!}{(r-1)!(n-r)!} f_X(x) (F_X(x))^{r-1} (1-F_X(x))^{n-r} \tag{8}$$

By using the equation (5) and equation (7) in equation (8), we will get required probability density function of r^{th} order statistics $X_{(r)}$ of length biased two parameter Suja distribution as

$$f_{x(r)}(x) = \frac{n!}{(r-1)!(n-r)!} \left(\frac{x\theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} (\alpha + x^4) e^{-\theta x} \right) \\ \times \left(\frac{1}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} (\alpha\theta^4 \gamma(2, \theta x) + \gamma(6, \theta x)) \right)^{r-1} \\ \times \left(1 - \frac{1}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} (\alpha\theta^4 \gamma(2, \theta x) + \gamma(6, \theta x)) \right)^{n-r}$$

Therefore, the probability density function of higher order statistic $X_{(n)}$ of length biased two parameter Suja distribution can be obtained as

$$f_{x(n)}(x) = \frac{n x \theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} (\alpha + x^4) e^{-\theta x} \\ \times \left(\frac{1}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} (\alpha\theta^4 \gamma(2, \theta x) + \gamma(6, \theta x)) \right)^{n-1}$$

and probability density function of first order statistic $X_{(1)}$ of length biased two parameter Suja distribution can be obtained as

$$f_{x(1)}(x) = \frac{n x \theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} (\alpha + x^4) e^{-\theta x} \\ \times \left(1 - \frac{1}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} (\alpha\theta^4 \gamma(2, \theta x) + \gamma(6, \theta x)) \right)^{n-1}$$

5. Entropy

The concept of entropy was given by German physicist Rudolf Clausius (1865) which is commonly associated with uncertainty, diversity or disorder. The term entropy is also a fundamental aspect and is applied in vast areas of research like probability and statistics, physics, communication theory and economics. Entropy of a random variable X is a measure of variation of uncertainty.

a. Renyi Entropy

The term Renyi entropy is important aspect in quantum information which can be applied as a measure of entanglement. The Renyi entropy was given by Alfred Renyi and is also important in ecology and statistics as index of diversity. For a given probability distribution, Renyi entropy of order β is given by

$$e(\beta) = \frac{1}{1-\beta} \log \left(\int f_l^\beta(x) dx \right)$$

Where $\beta > 0$ and $\beta \neq 1$

$$e(\beta) = \frac{1}{1-\beta} \log \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{x\theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} (\alpha + x^4) e^{-\theta x} \right)^\beta dx$$

$$e(\beta) = \frac{1}{1-\beta} \log \left(\left(\frac{\theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} \right)^\beta \int_0^\infty x^\beta (\alpha + x^4)^\beta e^{-\theta\beta x} dx \right) \tag{9}$$

Using binomial expansion of

$$(\alpha + x^4)^\beta = \sum_{k=0}^\infty \binom{\beta}{k} \alpha^{\beta-k} x^{4k}$$

Now equation (9) becomes

$$e(\beta) = \frac{1}{1-\beta} \log \left(\left(\frac{\theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} \right)^\beta \sum_{k=0}^\infty \binom{\beta}{k} \alpha^{\beta-k} x^{4k} \int_0^\infty x^\beta e^{-\theta\beta x} dx \right)$$

$$e(\beta) = \frac{1}{1-\beta} \log \left(\left(\frac{\theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} \right)^\beta \sum_{k=0}^\infty \binom{\beta}{k} \alpha^{\beta-k} \int_0^\infty x^{\beta+4k} e^{-\theta\beta x} dx \right)$$

$$e(\beta) = \frac{1}{1-\beta} \log \left(\left(\frac{\theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} \right)^\beta \sum_{k=0}^\infty \binom{\beta}{k} \alpha^{\beta-k} \int_0^\infty x^{(\beta+4k+1)-1} e^{-\theta\beta x} dx \right)$$

$$e(\beta) = \frac{1}{1-\beta} \log \left(\left(\frac{\theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} \right)^\beta \sum_{k=0}^\infty \binom{\beta}{k} \alpha^{\beta-k} \frac{\Gamma(\beta+4k+1)}{(\theta\beta)^{\beta+4k+1}} \right)$$

b. Tsallis Entropy

The term Tsallis entropy developed in 1988 as a generalization of Boltzmann-Gibbs (B.G) statistical properties initiated by Tsallis has focused a great deal to attention. This generalization of B-G statistics was proposed firstly by introducing the mathematical expression of Tsallis entropy for a continuous random variable is defined as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_\eta &= \frac{1}{\eta-1} \left(1 - \int_0^\infty f_l^\eta(x) dx \right) \\
 S_\eta &= \frac{1}{\eta-1} \left(1 - \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{x\theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} (\alpha + x^4) e^{-\theta x} \right)^\eta dx \right) \\
 S_\eta &= \frac{1}{\eta-1} \left(1 - \left(\frac{\theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} \right)^\eta \int_0^\infty x^\eta (\alpha + x^4)^\eta e^{-\eta\theta x} dx \right) \tag{10}
 \end{aligned}$$

Using binomial expansion of

$$(\alpha + x^4)^\eta = \sum_{i=0}^\infty \binom{\eta}{i} \alpha^{\eta-i} x^{4i}$$

Equation (10) becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_\eta &= \frac{1}{\eta-1} \left(1 - \left(\frac{\theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} \right)^\eta \sum_{i=0}^\infty \binom{\eta}{i} \alpha^{\eta-i} x^{4i} \int_0^\infty x^\eta e^{-\eta\theta x} dx \right) \\
 S_\eta &= \frac{1}{\eta-1} \left(1 - \left(\frac{\theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} \right)^\eta \sum_{i=0}^\infty \binom{\eta}{i} \alpha^{\eta-i} \int_0^\infty x^{\eta+4i} e^{-\eta\theta x} dx \right) \\
 S_\eta &= \frac{1}{\eta-1} \left(1 - \left(\frac{\theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} \right)^\eta \sum_{i=0}^\infty \binom{\eta}{i} \alpha^{\eta-i} \int_0^\infty x^{(\eta+4i+1)-1} e^{-\eta\theta x} dx \right) \\
 S_\eta &= \frac{1}{\eta-1} \left(1 - \left(\frac{\theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} \right)^\eta \sum_{i=0}^\infty \binom{\eta}{i} \alpha^{\eta-i} \frac{\Gamma(\eta+4i+1)}{(\eta\theta)^{\eta+4i+1}} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

6. Structural Properties

In this section, we will have derived the different statistical properties of length biased two parameter Suja distribution which include moments, harmonic mean, moment generating function and characteristic function.

a. Moments

Let X be the random variable represents length biased two parameter Suja distribution with parameters θ and α , then the r^{th} order moment $E(X^r)$ of developed new distribution can be obtained as

$$\mu_r' = E(X^r) = \int_0^\infty x^r f_l(x) dx$$

$$\mu_r' = \int_0^\infty x^r \frac{x\theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} (\alpha + x^4) e^{-\theta x} dx$$

$$\mu_r' = \int_0^\infty \frac{x^{r+1} \theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} (\alpha + x^4) e^{-\theta x} dx$$

$$\mu_r' = \frac{\theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} \int_0^\infty x^{r+1} (\alpha + x^4) e^{-\theta x} dx$$

$$\mu_r' = \frac{\theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} \left(\alpha \int_0^\infty x^{r+1} e^{-\theta x} dx + \int_0^\infty x^{r+5} e^{-\theta x} dx \right)$$

$$\mu_r' = \frac{\theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} \left(\alpha \int_0^\infty x^{(r+2)-1} e^{-\theta x} dx + \int_0^\infty x^{(r+6)-1} e^{-\theta x} dx \right) \tag{11}$$

After simplification of equation (11), we obtain

$$\mu_r' = E(X^r) = \frac{(\alpha\theta^4\Gamma(r+2) + \Gamma(r+6))}{\theta^r(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} \tag{12}$$

By using $r = 1, 2, 3$ and 4 in equation (12), we will obtain the first four moments about origin of length biased two parameter Suja distribution as

$$\mu_1' = \frac{(2\alpha\theta^4 + 720)}{\theta(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)}$$

$$\mu_2' = \frac{(6\alpha\theta^4 + 5040)}{\theta^2(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)}$$

$$\mu_3' = \frac{(24\alpha\theta^4 + 40320)}{\theta^3(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)}$$

$$\mu_4' = \frac{(120\alpha\theta^4 + 362880)}{\theta^4(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)}$$

$$\text{Variance} = \frac{(6\alpha\theta^4 + 5040)}{\theta^2(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} - \left(\frac{2\alpha\theta^4 + 720}{\theta(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} \right)^2$$

$$S.D(\sigma) = \sqrt{\left(\frac{(6\alpha\theta^4 + 5040)}{\theta^2(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} - \left(\frac{2\alpha\theta^4 + 720}{\theta(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} \right)^2 \right)}$$

b. Harmonic mean

The harmonic mean of length biased two parameter Suja distribution can be obtained as

$$H.M = E\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{1}{x} f_l(x) dx$$

$$H.M = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{1}{x} \frac{x\theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} (\alpha + x^4) e^{-\theta x} dx$$

$$H.M = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} (\alpha + x^4) e^{-\theta x} dx$$

$$H.M = \frac{\theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} \int_0^{\infty} (\alpha + x^4) e^{-\theta x} dx$$

$$H.M = \frac{\theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} \left(\alpha \int_0^{\infty} e^{-\theta x} dx + \int_0^{\infty} x^4 e^{-\theta x} dx \right)$$

$$H.M = \frac{\theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} \left(\alpha \int_0^{\infty} x^{(2)-2} e^{-\theta x} dx + \int_0^{\infty} x^{(5)-1} e^{-\theta x} dx \right) \quad (13)$$

After simplification of equation (13), we obtain

$$H.M = \frac{\theta(\alpha\theta^3 + 24)}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)}$$

c. Moment generating function and characteristic function

Suppose X be the random variable represents length biased two parameter Suja distribution with parameters θ and α , then the moment generating function of proposed distribution can be obtained as

$$M_X(t) = E(e^{tx}) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{tx} f_l(x) dx$$

By using Taylor's expansion, we get

$$M_X(t) = \int_0^{\infty} \left(1 + tx + \frac{(tx)^2}{2!} + \dots \right) f_l(x) dx$$

$$M_X(t) = \int_0^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^j}{j!} x^j f_l(x) dx$$

$$M_X(t) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^j}{j!} \mu_j'$$

$$M_X(t) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^j}{j!} \left(\frac{\alpha \theta^4 \Gamma(j+2) + \Gamma(j+6)}{\theta^j (\alpha \theta^4 + 120)} \right)$$

$$M_X(t) = \frac{1}{(\alpha \theta^4 + 120)} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^j}{j! \theta^j} (\alpha \theta^4 \Gamma(j+2) + \Gamma(j+6))$$

Similarly, the characteristic function of length biased two parameter Suja distribution can be obtained as

$$\varphi_X(t) = M_X(it)$$

$$\varphi_X(t) = \frac{1}{(\alpha \theta^4 + 120)} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{it^j}{j! \theta^j} (\alpha \theta^4 \Gamma(j+2) + \Gamma(j+6))$$

7. Bonferroni and Lorenz Curves

The bonferroni and Lorenz curves are oldest classical curves that was applied in economics in earlier times but now its application has been arising and is observing in various fields. The proposed curves are being applied in order to reveal the distribution of inequality in income and poverty. The bonferroni and Lorenz curves are given by

$$B(p) = \frac{1}{p\mu_1'} \int_0^q x f_l(x) dx$$

$$L(p) = pB(p) = \frac{1}{\mu_1'} \int_0^q x f_l(x) dx$$

$$\text{Where } \mu_1' = \frac{(2\alpha \theta^4 + 720)}{\theta(\alpha \theta^4 + 120)} \quad \text{and } q = F^{-1}(p)$$

$$B(p) = \frac{\theta(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)}{p(2\alpha\theta^4 + 720)} \int_0^q x \frac{x\theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} (\alpha + x^4) e^{-\theta x} dx$$

$$B(p) = \frac{\theta(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)}{p(2\alpha\theta^4 + 720)} \int_0^q \frac{x^2 \theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} (\alpha + x^4) e^{-\theta x} dx$$

$$B(p) = \frac{\theta^7}{p(2\alpha\theta^4 + 720)} \int_0^q x^2 (\alpha + x^4) e^{-\theta x} dx$$

$$B(p) = \frac{\theta^7}{p(2\alpha\theta^4 + 720)} \left(\alpha \int_0^q x^2 e^{-\theta x} dx + \int_0^q x^6 e^{-\theta x} dx \right) \tag{15}$$

Put $\theta x = t \Rightarrow x = \frac{t}{\theta}$

Also $\theta dx = dt \Rightarrow dx = \frac{dt}{\theta}$

As $x \rightarrow 0, t \rightarrow 0$ and as $x \rightarrow q, t \rightarrow \theta q$

After simplification of equation (15), we get

$$B(p) = \frac{1}{p(2\alpha\theta^4 + 720)} \left(\alpha\theta^4 \gamma(3, \theta q) + \gamma(7, \theta q) \right)$$

$$L(p) = \frac{1}{(2\alpha\theta^4 + 720)} \left(\alpha\theta^4 \gamma(3, \theta q) + \gamma(7, \theta q) \right)$$

8. Parameter Estimation and Fisher’s Information Matrix

In this section, we will derive and discuss the technique of maximum likelihood estimation to estimate the parameters of length biased two parameter Suja distribution. Consider X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n be a random sample of size n from the length biased two parameter Suja distribution, then the likelihood function can be stated as

$$L(x) = \prod_{i=1}^n f_i(x)$$

$$L(x) = \prod_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{x_i \theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} (\alpha + x_i^4) e^{-\theta x_i} \right)$$

$$L(x) = \left(\frac{\theta^6}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} \right)^n \prod_{i=1}^n \left(x_i \left(\alpha + x_i^4 \right) e^{-\theta x_i} \right)$$

$$L(x) = \frac{\theta^{6n}}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)^n} \prod_{i=1}^n \left(x_i \left(\alpha + x_i^4 \right) e^{-\theta x_i} \right)$$

The log likelihood function can be stated as

$$\begin{aligned} \log L &= 6n \log \theta - n \log(\alpha\theta^4 + 120) + \sum_{i=1}^n \log x_i \\ &+ \sum_{i=1}^n \log \left(\alpha + x_i^4 \right) - \theta \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

By differentiating the log likelihood equation (16) with respect to θ and α . We must obtain

the following normal equations

$$\frac{\partial \log L}{\partial \theta} = \frac{6n}{\theta} - n \left(\frac{4\alpha\theta^3}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} \right) - \sum_{i=1}^n x_i = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \log L}{\partial \alpha} = -n \left(\frac{\theta^4}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)} \right) + \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{(\alpha + x_i^4)} \right) = 0$$

The above likelihood equations are too complicated to solve it algebraically. Therefore, we employed the numerical technique Newton-Raphson method for estimating the parameters of new distribution.

To determine the confidence interval, we use the asymptotic normality results. We have that if $\hat{\varepsilon} = (\hat{\theta}, \hat{\alpha})$ which reveals the MLE of $\varepsilon = (\theta, \alpha)$. The result can be stated as

$$\sqrt{n}(\hat{\varepsilon} - \varepsilon) \rightarrow N_2(0, I^{-1}(\varepsilon))$$

Where $I^{-1}(\varepsilon)$ is Fisher's information matrix.

$$I(\varepsilon) = -\frac{1}{n} \begin{pmatrix} E \left(\frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial \theta^2} \right) & E \left(\frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial \theta \partial \alpha} \right) \\ E \left(\frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial \alpha \partial \theta} \right) & E \left(\frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial \alpha^2} \right) \end{pmatrix}$$

Here, we can describe

$$E\left(\frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial \theta^2}\right) = -\frac{6n}{\theta^2} - n\left(\frac{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)(12\alpha\theta^2) - (4\alpha\theta^3)^2}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)^2}\right)$$

$$E\left(\frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial \alpha^2}\right) = n\left(\frac{(\theta^4)^2}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)^2}\right) - \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{\left(\alpha + x_i^4\right)^2}\right)$$

$$E\left(\frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial \theta \partial \alpha}\right) = -n\left(\frac{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)(4\theta^3) - (4\alpha\theta^3)(\theta^4)}{(\alpha\theta^4 + 120)^2}\right)$$

Since ε is unknown, we estimate $I^{-1}(\varepsilon)$ by $I^{-1}(\hat{\varepsilon})$ and this can be used to determine the asymptotic confidence intervals for θ and α .

9. Application

In this section, we have applied and fitted a real data set to discuss the goodness of fit of length biased two parameter Suja distribution and then the performance of fit has been compared over two parameter Suja, quasi Suja, Suja, exponential and Lindley distributions. The real lifetime data set is given below.

The following real lifetime data set consists the time between failures for repairable items which was observed by Murthy et al. 2004 and discussed in Gamedani et al. 2017. The data set is given below as

Table 1: Data represents the time for failures of repairable items reported by Murthy et al. 2004

1.43	0.11	0.71	0.77	2.63	1.49	3.46
2.46	0.59	0.74	1.23	0.94	4.36	0.40
1.74	4.73	2.23	0.45	0.70	1.06	1.46
0.30	1.82	2.37	0.63	1.23	1.24	1.97
1.86	1.17					

In order to compute the model comparison criterion values along with the estimation of unknown parameters, the analysis is performed through the technique of R software. To explore performance of length biased two parameter Suja distribution over two parameter Suja, quasi Suja, Suja, exponential and Lindley distributions, we employ criterions like *AIC* (Akaike Information Criterion), *BIC* (Bayesian Information Criterion), *AICC* (Akaike Information Criterion Corrected) and $-2\log L$. The distribution is better obviously if it has the smaller criterion values of *AIC*, *BIC*, *AICC* and $-2\log L$. The formulae for calculating the criterions values are given below

$$AIC = 2k - 2\log L, \quad BIC = k \log n - 2\log L \quad \text{and} \quad AICC = AIC + \frac{2k(k+1)}{n-k-1}$$

Where n is the sample size, k is the number of parameters in statistical model and $-2\log L$ is the maximized value of log-likelihood function

Table 2: Shows Performance and Comparison of fitted Distributions

Distributions	MLE	S.E	-2logL	AIC	BIC	AICC
Length Biased Two Parameter Suja	$\hat{\alpha} = 2.426560$ $\hat{\theta} = 1.296910$	$\hat{\alpha} = 2.372657$ $\hat{\theta} = 1.672841$	79.26208	83.26208	86.06447	83.7065
Two Parameter Suja	$\hat{\alpha} = 0.1068611$ $\hat{\theta} = 2.7281389$	$\hat{\alpha} = 0.1203003$ $\hat{\theta} = 0.3467675$	86.74344	90.74344	93.54584	91.1878
Quasi Suja	$\hat{\alpha} = 0.2915087$ $\hat{\theta} = 2.7281622$	$\hat{\alpha} = 0.2980607$ $\hat{\theta} = 0.3468116$	86.74344	90.74344	93.54584	91.1878
Suja	$\hat{\theta} = 2.0912311$	$\hat{\theta} = 0.1425383$	90.10479	92.10479	93.50598	92.2476
Exponential	$\hat{\theta} = 0.6482287$	$\hat{\theta} = 0.1183495$	86.01075	88.01075	89.41195	88.1536
Lindley	$\hat{\theta} = 0.9762395$	$\hat{\theta} = 0.1345043$	83.09456	85.09456	86.49576	85.2374

From results given above in table 2, it is quite clear and evident that the length biased two parameter Suja distribution has the lesser *AIC*, *BIC*, *AICC* and $-2\log L$ values as compared to two parameter Suja, quasi Suja, Suja, exponential and Lindley distributions. Hence, it can be

revealed and is found that the length biased two parameter Suja distribution leads to a better fit over two parameter Suja, quasi Suja, Suja, exponential and Lindley distributions.

10. Conclusion

This present article suggested with a new transformation of two parameter Suja distribution termed as length biased two parameter Suja distribution. This particular new distribution is formulated by incorporating length biased model to its classical distribution. Its fundamental statistical properties such as moments, harmonic mean, survival function, hazard function, reverse hazard function, moment generating function, bonferroni and Lorenz curves, order statistics, Renyi entropy and Tsallis entropy have been studied. Furthermore, its parameters have been estimated by employing the maximum likelihood estimation. Additionally, the practicability and significance of the length biased two parameter Suja distribution has been investigated and analyzed by using a real lifetime data set. Hence, it can be concluded from the result that the length biased two parameter Suja distribution provides a quite satisfactory fit over two parameter Suja, quasi Suja, Suja, exponential and Lindley distributions.

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